

Statistical Analysis Plan

TRIAL FULL TITLE	PRedicting Outcomes For Crohn's disease using a moLecular biomarkEr (PROFILE) trial
EUDRACT NUMBER	
SAP VERSION	2.0
ISRCTN NUMBER	ISRCTN11808228
SAP VERSION DATE	12 MAY 2023
TRIAL STATISTICIAN	Simon Bond
TRIAL CHIEF INVESTIGATOR	Miles Parkes
SAP AUTHOR	Simon Bond

1 SAP Signatures

I give my approval for the attached SAP entitled Profile Final Analysis dated Version 2.0 12 MAY 2023

Chief Investigator

Name: Miles Parkes

Signature:

Date: 12th May 2023.

Statistician

Name: Simon Bond

Signature:

Date: 12 May 2023

PROFILE

Title: PROFILE Trial Statistical Analysis Plan

Date: 12 May 2023